

The Impact of Cash Management on Financial Performance of Quoted Selected Firms in Nigeria

ABUBAKAR Yakubu, OLAIFA Oluwafemi Olumuyiwa and UMARU
Dangana

Abubakar Yak & Co Chartered Accountants, FCT, Abuja
Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria
College of Education Gidan Waya

Abstract

This study examines the impact of Cash management on financial performance of selected quoted firms in Nigeria. The study has been conducted in different parts of the globe and in Nigeria with different findings which are mixed and inconclusive. The population of the study consists of ten (10) firms quoted on the Nigerian stock exchange as at 31st December 2024 out of which ten (10) firms were selected as samples for a period of Ten (10) years from 2015 to 2024 based on purposeful sampling technique. The study uses regression as a tool for analysis and adopted the correlational research design. The study shows that Inventory has no significant impact on financial performance of selected firms in Nigeria. Cash and cash equivalent has a positive significant impact on financial performance of quoted selected firms in Nigeria.

Keywords: Cash management, Cash and cash equivalent, inventory, and Leverage.

Introduction

Cash management is one of the key features of financial soundness in business. It is a very significant tool to a financial manager when it has to do with firms' business operations. Cash management has to do with simply the process of gathering and running cash flows. It is also known as treasury management which is the process that involves running and gathering cash flows from the operating investing and financing activities of a company. Cash management can be important for both individuals and companies. Cash is among the primary assets that individuals and companies use to pay their obligations and invest. Managing cash is what entities do on a day-to-day basis to take care of the inflows and outflows of their money. Proper cash management can improve an entity's financial situation and liquidity problems. Cash flows relating to operating activities are generally heavily focused on working capital which is impacted by Accounts Receivables and Accounts Payables changes. Investing and financing cash flows are usually extraordinary cash events that involve special procedures for funds.

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A company's working capital is the result of its current assets minus current liabilities. Working capital balances are important in cash flow management because they show the number of current assets a company has to cover its current liabilities.

Effective cash management enables a business to control its finances efficiently, reduce disruptions, and operate smoothly. This ensures continuous growth, improved profitability, and long-term sustainability.

Cash management plays a crucial role in determining the financial performance and overall sustainability of a business. Efficient management of cash ensures that an organization maintains sufficient liquidity to meet its short-term obligations while also investing excess funds profitably. Several authors and researchers have emphasized the strong relationship between effective cash management and improved financial performance. According to Pandey (2015), cash management involves planning and controlling cash inflows and outflows to ensure that a firm maintains adequate liquidity. He asserts that efficient cash management enhances a firm's ability to meet obligations on time, reduce financing costs, and ultimately improve profitability. Gitman (2009) also highlights that effective cash management enables firms to minimize the cost of holding cash while ensuring that sufficient funds are available for operational needs. This balance directly contributes to improved return on investment and profitability ratios, which are key indicators of financial performance. Similarly, Ross, Westerfield, and Jordan (2018) explain that cash management decisions are an integral part of working capital management. They argue that poor cash management can lead to liquidity crises, loss of business opportunities, and even insolvency, all of which negatively impact financial performance. Brigham and Ehrhardt (2014) further note that maintaining optimal cash levels enhances a firm's flexibility in responding to market changes, settling debts, and taking advantage of profitable investments. This flexibility strengthens financial performance by ensuring operational efficiency and cost reduction. In a study by Afza and Nazir (2009), it was found that firms with efficient cash management practices demonstrate higher profitability levels compared to those with weak cash control systems. Their findings suggest that managing cash flows effectively leads to better utilization of financial resources and improved organizational performance. Moreover, Deloof (2003) emphasizes that the speed of cash conversion and how quickly a firm converts sales into cash has a direct effect on profitability. Firms that manage their cash conversion cycle efficiently tend to perform better financially because they reduce financing costs and improve liquidity. In summary, efficient cash management positively influences financial performance via enhancing liquidity and solvency, reducing financing and operational costs, improving profitability and return on investment and supporting sustainable business growth. Therefore, effective cash management is not just a treasury function but a strategic component of financial performance management, ensuring that organizations remain both solvent and profitable in the long run.

Empirical studies conducted on Cash management and Financial performance which include studies Amini, Setiono, Pangaribuan and Princes (2018), Bari (2019), Faque (2021), Jajale (2020), Pandey (2019), Smirat (2016) Ugo & Egbubuzor (2022) are largely foreign and Nigerian.

This study in Nigeria has received little attention and the studies that have been conducted in Nigeria are not conclusive and could not provide adequate evidence on the impact of Cash management on financial performance as far as firms in the Oil and Gas and Consumer goods sectors are concerned. Those studies have provided mixed and inconclusive findings due to the data collected, methodology used and the industry used and to the best of our knowledge, among studies conducted in Nigeria, we have not seen a study that took into consideration the selected quoted firms from Oil and Gas and Consumer goods sectors. To this end, this study attempts to fill the gap by examining the impact of Cash management on financial performance of selected quoted firms of Consumer goods, industrial goods and conglomerate sectors in Nigeria. The main objective of the study is to examine the impact of Cash management on financial performance of quoted selected firms in Nigeria. The Specific objective of the study is to determine the extent to which inventory impacts on financial performance of quoted selected firms in Nigeria, to determine the extent to which cash and cash equivalent impacts on financial performance of quoted selected firms in Nigeria. In line with the specific objectives, Two hypotheses were formulated which are: HO1 Inventory has no significant impact on financial performance of quoted selected firms in Nigeria, Cash and cash equivalent has no significant impact on financial performance of Quoted selected firms in Nigeria.

Literature Review

Amini, Setiono, Pangaribuan and Princes (2018) examined the cash management practices towards financial performance of small and medium enterprises in Indonesia. They analyzed the current two elements of cash management practice, forecasting and cash mobilization done by SMEs in Indonesia and its impact on Return on Assets (ROA) and Gross Profit Margin (GPM). 90 SMEs in Java and Bali islands from April to July 2018 were employed. A 4-point scale questionnaire and regression analysis were employed to find significant relationships between the variables. The study found out that SMEs owners/managers often do forecasting and rarely do cash mobilization practices. The result also showed a significant relationship between cash management practices and ROA and a non-significant relationship between cash management practices and Gross Profit Margin (GPM). Bari (2019) studied the effect of Cash Management on Financial Performance of Food and Beverage Retailers in Puntland state of Somalia, A Case of Garowe District. They discovered the existing cash management practices of food and beverage retailers in Puntland and also identified the impacts of the established practices on their profitability and sustainability. Four specific objectives for the were: firstly cash conversion cycle of the food and beverage retailers in Puntland, secondly determining whether the retailers

had appropriate inventory management systems for their businesses, thirdly examining whether account receivable management policies for the retailers were in place and checking whether they are favorable for maximum profitability of their business and fourthly determining whether account payable management systems for the food and beverage retailers were in place and their effect to the business and to assess financial performance of the retailers basing on their financial statements from their business. Three theories of financial accounting were used accrual theory of accounting, trade credit theory and agency theory. Descriptive survey research design was employed. 39 foods and beverages retailers located in Garowe were used as samples for the study. They found out that the retailers had low liquidity ratio in their businesses and also identified that the cash flow from different retailers was not consistent. The majority of the retailers reported that the problem of low liquidity ratio resulted from the inability to pay their liabilities in due time due to fluctuation in food and beverages market trends in the area. It was also evident that the problem arose due to deprived managerial practices which include the incapability of the retailers to keep the path of their operations and to use the gained information in planning and management of their financial transactions. Faque (2021) examined the impact of Cash management strategies on financial performance: They provided a comprehensive literature review on existing theories and cash management practices that are useful in decision making and highlighted important theories including trade-off theory (TOT), transaction model, precautionary measures, financial hierarchy, and cash flow theory. They suggested that sound financial performance can be achieved through a hybrid approach and through adaptation and embracing innovations in cash management systems. Wanjuki, Githui and Omurwa (2021) investigated the relationship between cash management and financial performance of private hospitals in Nairobi County, Kenya. Descriptive design was adopted. The population of 25 private hospitals in Nairobi County was used and they collected primary data from the respondents which was quantitative and was analyzed through Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSSV18.0). Both descriptive and inferential analysis was used by the study. The result of the study showed that cash conversion cycle and cash budgeting had a positive and significant effect on financial performance of private hospitals. However, cash banking and cash flow forecasting had not significantly improved financial performance. Jajale (2020) opined the effect of cash management on the performance of commercial banks in Mogadishu, Somalia. They specifically looked at the effects of capital adequacy, Liquidity Management, receivables management and payables management on cash management in the performance of commercial banks in Mogadishu, Somalia. They employed a survey research design in data collection and non-probability sampling procedure particularly purposive sampling or judgmental sampling. They adopted a quantitative data collection method whereby data was gathered by the use of closed ended questionnaires. Data was analyzed using the software called Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) version 20 and results shown in terms of frequency distribution and percentages. From the data collected, 48 questionnaires were filled, 42 were returned and 6 missed which represent 88% response rate while 12% were missing. This response rate was

considered satisfactory to make conclusions for the study. The study results supported the view that cash management drivers had a significant effect on financial performance of commercial banks in Somalia. However, the influence of each driver varied from one bank to another. Pandey (2019) examined the impact of cash management on profitability in small manufacturing organizations. This study adopted correlational research design. Purposive sampling method was adopted. 80 samples were used. The sample structure consisted of small and medium manufacturing businesses in the Kirtipur Municipality. Data were collected using five point Likert Scale Questionnaires. They analyzed the data using mean, correlation and regression models. The result of the study showed that Cash management has an insignificant but positive effect on profitability. Smirat (2016) studied the effect of cash management practices on the financial performance of SMEs in Jordan. A structured questionnaire was used to collect primary data from the respondents which were analyzed to generate frequencies and percentages. The result of the study showed that only (32) percent from SMEs kept track of Cash Receipts and payment and the majority (67%) of respondents had no knowledge about cash control procedures. Eton *et al* (2019) investigated the effect of cash management on financial performance of business entities in Lira district. A cross sectional study design was adopted and structured and closed ended questionnaires were used to collect Data. The result of the study revealed that the aforementioned practices were not sustainable with time due to incompetence in forecasting receipts and payments. This led to a conclusion that cash management has an insignificant effect on financial performance. Ugo and Egbuhuzor (2022) investigated the effect of cash flow management on financial performance: Evidence from the pharmaceutical industry in Nigeria. Ex-post facto research design was adopted and a population of ten (10) listed pharmaceutical companies in Nigeria as listed by the Nigerian Exchange Group in 2021 was employed. Data were retrieved from the annual reports of the selected listed pharmaceutical companies from 2011 to 2020. Multiple regression analysis and the Pairwise Granger Causality tests were used to analyze the data gathered with the aid of EViews10 statistical software. The result of the study revealed a positive and insignificant effect of operating activities on liquidity, a positive and insignificant effect of investing activities on liquidity and a negative but significant effect of financing activities on the liquidity of listed pharmaceutical companies in Nigeria. Shrestha (2020) opined the impact of cash management on sustainability of small manufacturing business in Dhulikhel Municipality. They attempted to find the current position of cash management practices of small and medium manufacturing businesses. They specifically emphasized on the effect of cash management on profitability of small and medium manufacturing businesses and the effect of cash management and sustainability of small manufacturing businesses in Dhulikhel Municipality. Quantitative research paradigm and a sampling method targeted a sample of more than 50% of registered businesses in the chosen area. The result of the study revealed an insignificant relationship between Cash management and sustainability. Dibia (2022) examined the impact of cash management on financial performance of quoted manufacturing firms in Nigeria. Cash conversion cycle (CCC), Creditors

payment period (CPP), and Cash flow margin (CFM) were proxies of cash management. Arellano and Bond dynamic panel data estimation was employed in the analysis to address the potential effects of endogeneity in the relationship. The findings of the study revealed that Cash conversion cycle had a positive and significant impact on financial performance; Creditors' payment Period (CPP) had a positive impact on the firm financial performance, which is significant at 5%. Furthermore, cash flow margin (CFM) positively impacts financial performance, which is also significant at 5%. Oteyo (2018) assessed cash management and how it affects small and medium enterprises (SMEs) financial performance in Nakuru County, Kenya. Cash planning, cash and bank reconciliation, cash position and credit management were proxies for the independent variables and Net profit margin was used as proxy for financial performance. Many studies have been conducted with regard to SMEs and general financial performance, but none has since narrowed down to look into the cash management component and how it affects financial performance. Three theories were used namely; the pecking order theory, trade-off theory and Keynes liquidity theories. Survey study where a cross-sectional study of SMEs was adopted. 73 SMEs were examined using quota sampling as the design basis. 45 medium enterprises and 28 small enterprises were examined. Questionnaires and personal interviews were the collection instruments used. The target respondents were owners of SMEs and their managers. Descriptive and regression analysis were conducted with the help of SPSS software. The result of the study found that there was a strong positive correlation ($r=0.859$) between cash management and financial performance whereby 73.7% of performance of SMEs could be attributed to cash management. There was a significant relationship ($F = 19.60 (4,74), P=0.000$) between cash management and financial performance. Credit management ($p=0.003$) and cash planning ($p=0.003$) were significant. Waiganjo and Theuri (2019) examined the effect of cash management practices on financial performance of private universities in Kenya. They identified the effect of cash budgeting, to determine the effect of cash policies, to establish the effect accounting practices and to identify the effect of investing of surplus cash on the financial performance of private universities in Kenya. They were guided by free cash flow theory and decision usefulness theory. They targeted 35 private universities registered by Commission for university education and sought observations of 35 finance officers. Descriptive research design and a Census were adopted for data collection. Questionnaires were administered to the targeted population. Data was coded and analyzed using Statistical Packages for Social Sciences (SPSS) and Microsoft excel. Data analysis was presented using descriptive and inferential statistics. Descriptive statistics involved weighted average and percentages and inferential statistics involved regression and correlation analysis. The result of the findings showed that cash budgeting assisted in making cash forecasting and variance analysis, however, does not enhance budgetary control, spending of cash as planned, control of university spending habits and involvement of all departments; cash policy ensured proper cash management and safe custody of financial documentation, however did not ensure security and tracking of university funds and that financial controls were strictly followed; accounting practices enhanced tracking of business

transactions and preparation of financial statements but not keeping of daily cash receipts and payments; investing surplus cash did not show improved liquidity and profitability and returns being consistent with risk undertaken. The result of correlation analysis showed that at 1% level of significance cash budgeting, cash policies, accounting practices and investing surplus cash have a significant positive influence in determination of financial performance in private universities. The results from regression analysis revealed that cash budgeting accounts 21.9% magnitude in influencing financial performance; cash policy accounts 43.1% magnitude of influence on financial performance; accounting practices accounts 29.8% effect size in influencing financial performance in private universities. Hamza, Mutala and Antwi (2015) studied to assess cash management practices and its effect on the financial performance of SMEs in the Northern Region of Ghana. They adopted descriptive cross-sectional survey research design which allowed the collection of primary quantitative data through structured questionnaires. Target population was 1000 owner/managers of SMEs. Stratified random sampling technique was employed to obtain a sample of 300 SMEs comprising 164 trading 26 manufacturing, 10 hairstyling, 62 dressmaking, and 38 carpentry enterprises. Data were analyzed using both descriptive and inferential statistics. The finding of the study showed that SME financial performance was positively related to efficiency of cash management (ECM) at 1 per cent significance level. Harvest (2022) investigated the relationship between cash management practices and financial performance of listed deposit money banks in Nigeria between 2014 and 2020. The study sought to investigate the relationship between cash and bank balances and return on equity, investigate the relationship between cash conversion cycle and return on equity, investigate the relationship between cash turnover and return on equity and finally, investigate the extent firms size moderate the relationship between cash management practices and financial performance of listed deposit money banks in Nigeria. Four hypotheses were adopted. Ex-post facto research design was employed and twenty-three listed deposit money banks in the Nigeria Exchange Group were used for population. Five of the banks were selected using purposive sampling technique. The data used in this study were sourced from annual reports and statement of accounts of the selected deposit money banks. Cash and banks balances, cash conversion cycle and cash turnover were employed as the independent variables while return on equity was employed as the dependent variable. Firm size was adopted as control variable. Descriptive statistics and ordinary least Square regression were employed in analyzing the data. The result of the study revealed that there is a positive and significant relationship between cash and banks balances and return on equity; there is a negative but significant relationship between cash conversion cycle and return on equity; there is a positive and significant relationship between cash turnover and return on equity and finally, firm size had positive and significant moderating influence on the relationship between cash management practices and financial performance. Based on the foregoing, the study concluded that there is a positive and significant relationship between cash management practices and financial performance of listed deposit money banks in Nigeria. Odhwa (2022) assessed the influence of cash flow management activities on the

financial performance of industrial firms listed at Nairobi securities exchange, Kenya. They examined the influence of cash flow management from operating activities, investing activities and financing activities and how they influence financial performance of industrial firms listed at the Nairobi securities exchange, Kenya. Theories which include Keynesian theory of money, free cash flow theory and cash flow management theory were used. The study adopted causal research design. The target population comprised eight manufacturing firms listed at the NSE where the study adopted a census from 2017 to year 2021. A data abstraction tool was used to collect secondary data. It adopted the panel regression model. Descriptive statistics (mean and standard deviation) and panel regression analysis was used to analyze data. The diagnostic tests were carried out before the actual analysis. The result of the study revealed that cash flow management from operating activities had a statistically insignificant influence on the financial performance of manufacturing firms ($p=0.275>0.05$). Cash flow management from investing activities had a statistically insignificant influence on financial performance of manufacturing firms ($p=0.125>0.05$). Wesonga (2017) analyzed the influence of cash management practices on performance of SSEs in Mbale town, Kenya. They determined the effect of maintaining business records on performance; establish the effect of preparing cash budget on performance and determine the effect of management of cash conversion cycle on performance. They anchored on the monetary theory and operating cycle theory of cash management. They employed the correlation study design. A population of 150 SSEs was used. Reliability of questionnaires was tested on pilot data from 10 respondents which alpha coefficients greater than .701 implying internal consistency. The content validity test was done using expert reviewers. Primary data was obtained using semi-structured questionnaires self-administered to the owners of the SSEs in Mbale town and secondary data from records in relevant offices. Data was analysed using Pearson correlation and multiple regression. The result of the findings revealed that business record keeping had a positive significant predictor of performance ($\beta = .353$ ($p = .000$); cash budgeting a positive significant predictor of performance ($\beta = .215$ ($p = .018$) and that management of cash conversion cycle a positive significant predictor of performance ($\beta = .449$ ($p = .000$). Mungal (2014) opined cash management on profitability and sustainability of small retail businesses in Tongaat area, Kwazulu Natal. They identified the current cash management practices of small retail businesses in the Tongaat area and identify the impact of such practices on their profitability and sustainability. Descriptive, cross sectional study, using a quantitative research paradigm was adopted and a non-probability sampling method targeted a sample of 69 businesses in the chosen area. The sample structure consisted of small retail businesses in the Tongaat area of KwaZulu-Natal. The result of the findings showed a significant relationship between drawing budgets and sustainability. Onyemaechi and Nneka (2020) investigated the influence of cash management on financial performance of selected manufacturing companies in Nigeria. The population was fifty five (55) manufacturing firms quoted on the Nigerian Stock Exchange (NSE) with a sample size of twenty-six (26) manufacturing companies purposively selected from the consumer and industrial goods sub-sectors. Ex-post facto research design was

employed. Secondary data was obtained from Annual reports of sampled companies as provided by individual companies and Nigerian Stock Exchange (NSE) website. The panel least square regression analysis was employed in validating the hypotheses. The result of the study revealed a significant negative effect of cash management on returns on assets and Tobin's Q. Returns on equity was negative and non-significant. Rosemary, Prince, Jack and Fausat (2021) examined the impact of cash flow management on industrial firms' performance in Nigeria. They established the liquidity-viability link in quoted non-financial firms in Nigeria. They used the regression model predominantly and also ignore the widely accepted econometric process of a pre and post diagnostic test. They focused on 13 quoted non-financial sectors in Nigeria firms from 1999-2020. The preliminary test was conducted to determine the best fit model. The result of the study showed that Liquidity proxy by the current ratio significantly influenced ROE and non-significantly on ROE when proxy by the cash flow ratio. Findings also divulged a bidirectional nexus between current ratio, cash flow ratio, and ROE and a non-causal nexus with other variables. Abioro (2013) examined the impact of cash management on the performance of manufacturing companies in Nigeria-A study of Cadbury Nigeria Plc. The researcher used both secondary and primary data for data collection. For clear analysis, they used two broad variables; the dependent variable which is performance and the independent variable which is Cash management. Two different hypotheses were formulated and tested using descriptive statistics and correlation coefficients techniques were used. The results of the study revealed a significant relationship exists between cash management and the performance of manufacturing companies in Nigeria. Chari, Gubo Mato, and Kennedy Nyariki. (2024) investigated how cash management influences the financial performance of savings and credit cooperative societies in Meru County Kenya. The study applied pecking order theory to cash and short-term securities management. The study selected representatives from the entire population using a simple random sampling method to have 13 customer care officers, 34 tellers, 28 back-office staff, and 36 loans officers, totaling 111 respondents. A descriptive research design was used to gather data from 24 deposit and non deposit Saccos in Meru County. Quantitative and Qualitative data were collected using closed ended questionnaires and financial statements. Descriptive statistics such as frequency, percentage, and mean were calculated. The findings of the study showed that Sacco management provided insights into how the management of cash assets can be optimized to enhance the liquidity of the institutions. Emmanuel & Edafiaje (2024) examined cash management and its effect on financial performance (FP) of deposit money banks (DMBs) in Nigeria from the period of 2013 to 2022 (10years). CA proxied with Cash flows from operating activities to total assets (CFOATA), Cash flows from investing activities to total assets (CFIATA), Cash flows from financing activities to total assets (CFFATA), Year ended cash balance to total assets (YECBTA) and Bank Size (BSZ) (independent variables) and FP proxied with Return on Assets (ROA). The Ex-Post Facto research design was employed. Data on CA and FP were obtained from the annual reports and accounts of ten (10) DMBs listed in Nigeria Exchange Group that has international presence. Descriptive statistics was employed followed by the correlation analysis used to

ascertain the co-movement of the independent variables in relation to the dependent variable and several diagnostics tests. Multiple Regression analysis was employed with the aid of E-VIEW version 9.0. The findings of study showed that CA used has mixed effects on ROA of DMBs in Nigeria. However, majority of the independent variables such CFFATA, YECBTA and BSZ has significant effects on ROA of DMBs while CFOATA and CFIATA established an insignificant effects on ROA of DMBs in Nigeria.

Methodology

This research adopted correlation research design and was considered adequate and appropriate for this study because it describes the statistical relationship between independent variables of the study (Cash and cash equivalent & Inventory) and the dependent variable (Return on Equity). The population consists of selected firms from Oil and Gas and Consumer goods Sector namely Conoil Plc, Champion Breweries Plc, Dangote Sugar Refinery Plc, Flour Mills Nigeria Plc, Forte Oil Plc, Honeywell Flour Mills Plc, MRS oil Nigeria Plc, Nestle Nigeria Plc, Oando Plc, Total Nigeria Plc quoted on the Nigerian Stock Exchange as at 31st December 2021 and covered a period of Ten (10) years (2015-2024). A purposeful sampling technique was employed to select the sample. The sample selected is: In line with this, the sample size is all the ten (10) selected quoted firms on the Nigerian stock exchange namely Conoil Plc, Champion Breweries Plc, Dangote Sugar Refinery Plc, Flour Mills Nigeria Plc, Forte Oil Plc, Honeywell Flour Mills Plc, MRS oil Nigeria Plc, Nestle Nigeria Plc, Oando Plc, Total Nigeria Plc. The study employed panel data using statistical package for social sciences (SPSS 25) and Ordinary Least Square (OLS) method adopted in this study is a parametric statistical test that is based on a number of assumptions, the violation of which could affect the reliability of the results. The Pearson correlation and t-test statistics were used for inferential analysis. Two of the most commonly encountered problems addressed in this study relate to normal distribution of the variables and descriptive statistics was used to test for normality of data.

Model Specification

The model that was used to test the hypothesis formulated for this study is presented below. The null Hypothesis is tested considering the results for the P-values at 1%, 5% and 10% level of significance.

$$ROE = f (INVENT\beta_1 + CCE\beta_2 + LEV\beta_3)$$

$$ROE = \alpha + \beta_1 INVENT + CCE\beta_2 + LEV\beta_3 + \epsilon_i$$

Where

α = the intercept

ROE = Profit after Tax divided by Total Equity.

INVENT = the Closing Balance of Inventory

CCE = the Closing Balance of Cash and Cash Equivalent which is

LEV = the total liabilities divided by total assets.

ϵ_t = error term

Leverage is a controls variable.

Data Presentation

This part presents the results of the descriptive statistics and regression results on the impact of Cash management on financial performance of selected quoted firms in Nigeria. Two explanatory variables and One (1) control variable are employed for the purpose of explaining and predicting the impact of Cash management on financial performance of selected quoted firms in Nigeria.

Test of Normality

The normality tests are supplementary to the graphical assessment of normality. For this study, Z skewness and Z Kurtosis are used to test for normality of the four (2) independent variables; namely Inventory, Cash and cash Equivalent. The Z skewness was computed as skewness divided by standard error of skewness and the Z kurtosis was computed as kurtosis divided by standard error of kurtosis.

Table 4.2.1 shows the skewness, kurtosis and Z skewness and Z kurtosis.

Table 1 Descriptive Statistics Table for the Variables

Variables	Skewness	Standard Error	Z Skewness	Kurtosis	Standard Error	Z Kurtosis
INVENT	2.881	0.241	11.954	10.554	0.478	22.079
CCE	2.348	0.241	9.743	7.600	0.478	15.900

This table shows the normality test for Inventory and Cash and cash equivalent

In small samples like that of this study in which the number of observations is 100, values of Z skewness and Z kurtosis greater or lesser than 1.96 are sufficient to establish normality of the data. The result of Skewness for Inventory is 2.881. The Z skewness of Inventory is 11.954 which is more than 1.96 shows that the data is normal which indicates that the data for Inventory relates linearly to the dependent variable (Return on Equity). The results of the Kurtosis for Inventory is 10.554 and the Z kurtosis of Inventory is 22.079 is more than 1.96 and therefore, is normal which indicates that the data for Inventory relates linearly to the

dependent variable (Return on Equity). The result of Skewness for Cash and Cash Equivalent is 2.348. The Z skewness of Cash and cash Equivalent is 9.743 which is more than 1.96 shows that the data is normal which indicates that the data for Cash and cash Equivalent relates linearly to the dependent variable (Return on Equity). The results of the Kurtosis for Cash and cash Equivalent is 7.6 and the Z kurtosis of Cash and cash Equivalent is 15.9 which is more than 1.96 and therefore, is normal which indicates that the data for Cash and cash Equivalent relates linearly to the dependent variable (Return on Equity). Ghasemi and Zahediasl (2012).

Table 2. Cash Management impact on Financial performance

Variable	Coefficient	T – value	P – value
Constant	0.156	2.910	0.019
INVENT	0.99	0.999	0.320
CCE	0.262	2.549	0.012
LEV	0.407	4.489	0.000
R	0.520		
R ²	0.270		
Adj R ²	0.247		
F stat	11.837		
F-Sig	0.000		
DW	1.695		

Source: Author’s computation using SPSS 25

The estimated equation of the study is presented as follows:

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$$\text{ROE} = 0.156 + 0.99 (\text{INVENT}) + 0.262 (\text{CCE}) + 0.407 (\text{LEV}).$$

Financial performance would be equal to 0.156 when all other variables are held to zero. One-unit change of Cash management all other variables remain constant, would increase Cash management by 0.156. The regression result of the study shows that the beta coefficient in respect of Inventory is (0.99) and the t-value is (0.999) and it is not significant. This means that, as far as selected firms of oil and gas and consumer goods sectors are concerned, inventory has no significant impact on financial performance of quoted selected firms in Nigeria. The implication of this is that, the higher the inventory, the lower the financial performance of quoted selected firms in Nigeria. This provides evidence of accepting the hypothesis stating that inventory has no significant impact on financial performance of quoted selected firms in Nigeria.

The regression result of the study shows that the beta coefficient in respect of Cash and cash equivalent is (0.262) and the t-value is (2.549) and it is significant at 1%. This means that, as far as selected firms of oil and gas and consumer goods sectors are concerned, Cash and cash equivalent has a positive significant impact on financial performance of quoted selected firms in Nigeria. The implication of this is that, the higher the Cash and cash equivalent, the higher the financial performance of quoted selected firms in Nigeria. This provides evidence of rejecting the hypothesis stating that Cash and cash equivalent has no significant impact on financial performance of quoted selected firms in Nigeria.

The impact of the Cash management is able to explain the dependent variable up to (52%). This shows a positive relationship as indicated by the R value and the remaining (48%) are controlled by other factors. Similarly, the result of the F- statistic shows the overall fitness of the model. The F- statistic has a value of (11.837) and is significant at 1% which implies that the model is fit because it is significant at all levels of significance. Durbin Watson of (1.695) shows that there is no problem of autocorrelation in the data set (Gujarati, 2004).

Findings of the Study

Inventory has no significant impact on financial performance of quoted selected firms in Nigeria.

Cash and cash equivalent has a positive significant impact on financial performance of quoted selected firms in Nigeria.

Conclusions

This study has contributed to findings on Accounting Research in Nigeria. It investigated whether cash management impacted on financial performance of quoted selected firms in Nigeria. The study concludes that Cash and cash equivalent has a positive significant impact on financial performance of quoted selected oil and gas and consumer goods firms in Nigeria.

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